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ECONOMIC INTEGRATION OF ARMENIAN DIASPORA IN RUSSIA

Poghosyan G.A. Professor of Sociology, Institute of Philosophy, Sociology and Law, Armenian National Academy of Sciences.

Poghosyan R.M. PhD in Psychology, Institute of Philosophy, Sociology and Law, Armenian National Academy of Sciences.

Abstract

Diasporas are a common element of political life almost all over the world. Nowadays, the role and activity of diasporas in international cooperation have increased significantly. It is difficult to imagine the history of the Armenian people without of its diaspora, which today makes up almost two-thirds of its total number. In the Russia is the largest and relatively early formed Armenian diaspora in the world. The article analyzes the stages of the formation of Armenian diaspora in Russia and level of its integration to the society using factual material and based on the analysis of the results of the sociological study of Armenians in the Moscow, Krasnodar and Stavropol regions of Russia. Specially for this porpoise the methodological strategy of applied sociological survey and the tools for studying the current Armenian diaspora's socio-economic integration into the Russian society have been created.

Keywords: Armenians, diaspora, Russia, integration, society.

Introduction

The term diaspora as known comes from the Old Greek *diaspora* or *diaserein*, which means to disperse, scatter. The word "diaspora" is first recorded in Greek translation of the Hebrew Bible - "Septuagint". Since it arose as a result of the translation of biblical texts, it retained religious connotations for a long time. (Militarev, 1999: 28-29). In Orthodoxy, the diaspora was a new part of the Christian community that was not part of the historically established local churches. Diaspora was recognized as voluntary residence in an alien environment, in isolation from the main mass of believers. (Kasatkin, 2011:72-79). "The word 'diaspora' has leapt from its previously confined use – mainly concerned with the dispersion of Jews, Greeks, Armenians and Africans away from their natal homelands – to cover the cases of many other ethnic groups, nationalities and religions". (Routledge Handbook of Diaspora Studies, 2019: 1-17)

Diaspora is a Greek term for a nation or part of a nation separated from its own state or territory and dispersed among other nations but preserving its own national culture. (Dubnow 1931: 126). A typical case of diaspora is presented by the Armenians, many of whom have voluntarily lived outside their small national territory for centuries. For the first time, diaspora is understood as a category with different instances. The American sociologist Robert Park use it, applying to the members of different Asian groups living far from their countries (Park, 1939: 38). Note that the Armenian language has long had an own-name for the word diaspora - "*spyurk*", which means dispersion. It is formed precisely from the Armenian verb "*sprel*" - to scatter, to spread.

Later, in the XX century, the confessional understanding of the diaspora was replaced by an ethnic and national one. Robert Park the founder of the sociological school of Chicago introduced the concept of diaspora into scientific circulation. (Park, 1939). The following were named as classic diasporas: Armenian, Greek, Jewish communities, etc. The famous American researcher of diasporas Khachik Tölölyan (an Armenian, originally from Western Armenia) emphasized the relative nature of the diaspora, saying that the diaspora, as a rule, fixes a certain identity at a certain moment, which at another moment may be fixed differently. (Tölölyan K. 1996: 3-36)

The concept of diaspora has come a long way historically. Nowadays, diasporas can be religious (Sikhs), ethnic (Armenians, Jews) and even racial (Africans). As a rule, belonging to a diaspora is understood as the initial belonging of a migrant to a given ethnic group, and not as a result of his voluntary choice. American scientist Rogers Brubaker put forward the concept of "diaspora cataclysm", in which he tried to characterize such a new phenomenon of the XX century as the formation of ethnic minorities as a result of the collapse of multinational empires. (Brubaker, R. 2000).

In this regard, sometimes there is a blurring of the boundaries between the conceptual fields of the term "community" and "diaspora". Depending on how much certain ethnic groups fall under these criteria, they can be described as diasporas or not. The most complete set of such criteria in scientific literature was once developed by the famous American political scientist William Safran. In terms of these criteria, he underlain that man can "legitimately speak" of the Armenian, Greek, Palestinian, Chinese etc. diasporas. He mentioned: "The Armenian diaspora condition resembles that of the Jews most closely. Armenian ethnicity and the solidarity of the Armenian community are based on a common religion and language, a collective memory of national independence in a circumscribed territory, and a remembrance of betrayal, persecution, and genocide". (Safran, 1991: 87).

According to United Nations Report in 2019, India was the leading country of origin of international migrants, with 17.5 million persons living abroad. Migrants from Mexico constituted the second largest "diaspora" (11.8 million), followed by China (10.7 million), the Russian Federation (10.5 million). (UN, *International Migration 2019: Report*: p. iV)

Armenian Diaspora in Russia

Armenia has the largest global Diaspora community, in proportion to the size of its national population. (Armenia's Diaspora, 2014). Currently, Armenians live in 120 countries of the world, in which the total number of the Armenian Diaspora is about 8 million (Fig. 1). There are about 8-10 million Armenians currently living outside the country, where the own population is estimated at around 2.9 million. Largest Armenian communities are based in Russia (2.3 million), the United States (1.5 million), the France (400,000), the Lebanon (230,000) and other countries. (Armenia's Diaspora, 2014). Most of the Armenians living in more than 100 countries of the world have citizenship of these countries, and about 20% are the labor migrants.

According to numerous sociological studies we have conducted in Armenia over the past 30 years, the main flow of labor migrants (about 80%) went to the Russian Federation. (Karakashian, Poghosyan, 2003: 225-243; Poghosyan, 2011; Poghosyan, 2014). For the period 1997-2006 more than one million people emigrated from Armenia (Poghosyan, 2006). During the period 1998-2002, according to the official data, the number of Armenians in Russia increased from 532.4 thousand to 1,130.5 thousand people (Population of Russia 2003-2004: 2006). And according to the 2010 census of Russian Federation, Armenians numbered 1,182,388 people (Population of Russia: numbers, dynamics, statistics: 2020). The flow of Armenian migrants to Russia annually amounted to about 13-15 thousand people (Demographic Yearbook of Russia: 2019). In 2019-2020 Migration flows, as well as tourist flows, have sharply decreased due to the global COVID-19 pandemic in the world. But then migration movements in Armenian society again increased significantly.

Today the largest Armenian diaspora in Russian Federation, which is comparable to the current population of Armenia of about 2.9 million people. Armenians lived and worked in Russia for a whole millennium. The Armenian diaspora, which formed in Russia in the middle centuries, is a conventional diaspora with deep historical roots. Its influence on the economy, social policy, culture, interethnic relations and other spheres of life of the population in Russia and country of origin is steadily increasing. (Topilin, 2021: 110).

The first information about Armenians in Ancient Russia dates back to the 10th–11th centuries. The number of Armenians in the Russian Empire was constantly increasing. After the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, a new and largest migration outflow from Armenia headed into Russia. This was mainly a flow of labor migrants who went to the many cities of the Russian Federation in search of job. The post-Soviet Armenian migration over the past twenty-five years totally amounted to slightly more than a million people. The main Russian places where the Armenian labor migrants work are three historical regions of residence of the Armenian diaspora in Russia. According to the 2010 Russian census, slightly less than 300,000 Armenians lived in Moscow and the Moscow region. 280,000 Armenians lived in Krasnodar Krai (region), and 160,000 Armenians lived in Stavropol Krai (region) (Integration VS Repatriation, 2022: 130). These are the three regions of the Russian Federation with the most Armenian population.

According to the data of the State Migration Service of the Republic of Armenia (State Migration Service of RA, 2019) and based on sociological research, approximate estimate of migration flows from Armenia is about 1.1 million people left Armenia between 1988 and 2001. During the 2002-2007 about 25,000 people left the country annually, plus about 60,000 were the annual seasonal migrants. Thus, the average estimate number of migrants over these 5 years was about 30,000 per year (Integration VS Repatriation, 2022: 132). The majority (80%) of Armenian migrants went to Russia. The main reasons for migration include economic, political, military and psychological factors.

New opportunities for continued development of the Armenian diaspora opened up along with the creation of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) in the post-soviet space. With the Armenia's accession in 2015 to the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), the Armenian diaspora at least maintained its numbers due to the stability of the number of people arriving in Russia, until the COVID-19 in 2020. In 2015 they were 45 670 people; in 2016 they were 43 929 people; in 2017 – 46 898; in 2018 – 46 442, and in 2019 – 71 984 people (Federal State Statistics Service, 2022). In 2021, the migration flow from Armenia increased to 103 thousand people (Eurasianet, 2021). The secret of the advancement of the Armenian diaspora as an ethnocultural phenomenon is rooted in the peculiarities of formation of its social and economic potential throughout the long history of good neighbor relations with Russia. (Topilin, 2021: 116).

The depopulation processes that have begun in Armenia today pose for the country's leadership the task of stimulating birth rate and organizing a mechanical influx of population through the repatriation of Armenians from abroad. In this regard, the problems of the integration of the Armenian Diaspora in Russia or its partial repatriation acquire special demographic and economic significance.

The main problem of the Armenian Diaspora is, of course, the preservation of national identity. The younger generation of Armenians in the Diaspora does not speak Armenian well enough, approximately 60-70% do not use written Armenian at all. The number of mixed marriages is growing sharply. In addition, in some countries there is the only one Armenian church (or prayer house), and therefore Armenians attend the Orthodox Churches. Here we would like to represent the results of our joint sociological project with the Institute of Demographic Research of the Russian Academy of Sciences, dedicated to studying the socio-economic well-being of Armenian Diaspora, its integration into the Russian economy, also the terms and conditions of its repatriation (Poghosyan, Osadchaya, 2024: 133-147).

In the scientific literature of recent years, the methodological foundations of the study of the theory and phenomenon of diasporas (Brubaker, 2005: 1-19; Safran, 1991: 83-99; Tölölyan, 1996: 3-15), the role of diasporas in the context of ensuring Russia's national security (Lubskiy, 2016: 63-73; Avdashkin, 2015: 131-137; Integration of migrants, 2018), theoretical problems of studying the adaptation of migrants in the host society (Khamidulin, 2016: 49-60; Endryushko, 2017: 45-70), as well as works analyzing various aspects of the activities of the Armenian diaspora have been revealed (Tirabyan, 2018; Shapovalov, 2015: 13-15; Gevorkyan, 2020: 102-114). There are different viewpoints in regard to the activity of the Armenian diaspora in Russia.

The certain researchers claim that this diaspora has a high potential and is very active (Galyapina, 2021: 104). However, the issues of integration of Armenian migrants in Russia have not been specifically analyzed sufficiently.

Survey methodology

The sociological survey of the integration behavior of Armenian migrants was conducted in 2021-2022 as part of the joint research project "The Armenian Diaspora of Russia in the Context of Integration Processes in the EAEU". The sociological study in Russian Federation was done among the 1,273 Armenian migrants in Moscow and region (658 people), in the Krasnodar region (310 people) and in Stavropol region (305 people). In Armenia 500 families of Armenian migrants were surveyed in 33 cities of the republic. Additionally, deep interviews were done among the 30 Armenian experts on migration and diaspora issues.

In the spring of 2022, our research team began developing a program for a nationally representative sociological survey among the adult population of the Republic of Armenia. Basic concepts, categories, methodology and key units of research were developed, as well as a list of thematic blocks and questions for inclusion in the questionnaire of sociological research. The empirical sociological study was carried out by the professionals of Armenian Sociological Association, using the personal interviews at homes of 1500 respondents - permanent residents of Armenia. The methodology of empirical sociological survey, sampling methodology, questionnaire design (included more than 50 questions) the guideline of the interview and field control were used during the sociological survey according to the international standards by the professionals of Armenian Sociological Association (ASA), which is the national member of International Sociological Association (since 1992), European Sociological Association (since 2006) and ESOMAR (1998-2017).

During the empirical study the multistage nationwide representative random sample was used in August-September of 2022. The study was conducted by personal face-to-face (F2F) interviews in the homes of respondents, via using the route sampling technique. The final selection of respondents was made using the simplified Kish method. The sample confidence level correspondence coefficient is 97%. The sampling error does not exceed the interval $\pm 2.5\%$ for the entire sample. The results obtained during the field research, after the preliminary control, editing and the procedure for closing of open questions, were entered into the database and subjected to statistical processing by using the SPSS special program for statistical analyzing of sociological information.

Patterns of Integration

The most important indicator of the degree of integration of migrants is their position in the labor market of receiving country. Among our respondents in Russia, 6 out of 10 were working, 2 working and study, and about 2 only study. The employment structure of members of the Armenian diaspora in Russia differs significantly from the employment structure of migrants from the other countries: they are more often engaged in highly skilled, intellectual work. Thus, among those surveyed Armenians were worked in the different sectors of Russian economy. (Table 1).

Table 1

	Working sector	Percent, %
1.	Service sector	21.8
2.	Trade	20.7
3.	Education	10.5
4.	Construction	10.0

5.	Healthcare	7.9
6.	Industry	5.6
7.	Not worked	23.5
	Total	100

Overall, among them, people working in these sectors of the economy had different skills and held the following positions (Table 2).

Table 2

	Work position	Percent, %
1.	Skilled employees	46.3
2.	Unskilled workers	13.3
3.	Individual entrepreneurs or self-employed	11.0
4.	Management position	8.8
5.	Entrepreneurs and businessmen	7.8
6.	Other	12.8
	Total	100

Immigrants from Armenia are more active than migrants from other CIS countries in settling in their new place of residence. According to a nationwide survey of labor migrants conducted in 2017 in Russian regions, the majority of migrants who indicated being in a better position in terms of housing availability turned out to be among migrants from Armenia 75.3%, with 36% - from the republics of Central Asia (Osadchaya, 2019). The ethnic entrepreneurship is an important factor in the formation and development of the economic potential of the Armenian diaspora. A sharp leap in its development occurred in the mid-1990s after the first refugees from Armenia arrived in the southern regions of Russia (Ryazantsev, 2000: 80). The presence and implementation of an entrepreneurial initiative has an ethnically distinctive adaptation criterion. The data of a sociological survey conducted in the Stavropol region at the turn of the XXI century showed an increase in entrepreneurial activity among all migrants. However, while the share of all migrants who own a business equals 11-13% of the respondents, Armenian migrants have a business potential that is about 2-3 times higher than Russians, and the effectiveness of its application in practice is 1.5-2 times higher than the same indicator among the Russians (Ryazantsev, 2000: 80).

The degree of integration of members of the Armenian diaspora is characterized by the assessment of various aspects of everyday life in Russia: income status, housing conditions, organization of free time. The structure of the Armenian diaspora in Russia includes a wide range of group characteristics, indicating its multi-layered nature. Such heterogeneity negatively affects the social cohesion of the community. Empirically, the Armenian diaspora could not be too much homogeneous, but this multi-layered nature of special cultural codes does not mean its fragmentation and disunity. Thus, 76.5% of respondents consider the Armenian diaspora in Russia to be united, 83.5% believe that the majority of Armenians in the diaspora are always ready to help their compatriots (Integration VS Repatriation, 2022: 76). Public associations play an important role in the consolidation of the Armenian diaspora. The most famous of them are the "Union of Armenians of Russia", "Armenians of Russia", "Association of Armenian Youth" and "Assembly of Armenians" (Soyuz Armyan Rossii, 2025).

Currently, there are 250 Armenian communities and unions, 65 youth organizations, about 230 Armenian Sunday schools, colleges and preschool institutions, 72 churches operating in the Russian Federation; 45 titles of printed publications are published. Back in 2000, the "Union of Armenians of Russia" was established in Moscow - a large Armenian organization operating in 63 republics, territories and regions, with regional branches throughout the country.

Since 2018, a new public organization, the “Union of Armenians of Russia”, has also begun operating in Moscow¹. Many centers and departments of Armenian studies operate in Russian cities like Moscow, Nizhny Novgorod, St. Petersburg, Yekaterinburg, Sochi, Simferopol and Pyatigorsk. Armenian public organizations, national-cultural and cultural-educational unions, and cultural centers operate. In 2011, a new Armenian temple complex was opened in Moscow, which became the residence of the Head of the Novo-Nakhichevan and Russian Diocese of the Armenian Apostolic Church. As before, Armenians in Russia are engaged in entrepreneurial activity, creating commercial enterprises, banking institutions, brokerage firms, farming and construction organizations in rural areas of the Krasnodar and Stavropol Territories. As already noted, the regions of Russia with the highest Armenian population are Moscow and the Moscow Region, St. Petersburg, the Rostov Region, the Krasnodar and Stavropol Krajs (regions).

In Krasnodar Krai Armenians settled in the XV-XVI centuries, when the Turks occupied Crimea and the local Armenians were forced to flee to the North Caucasus of Russia, namely to Circassia (now the Republic of Adygea of the Russian Federation). In 1873-1824 Circassian Armenians gradually began to move to Kuban (which then joined Russia). And already in 1839, four Armenian villages united into one community called the Armenian Aul, which was later renamed Armavir. Beginning in 1860, the process of moving Armenians from Western Armenia (on the territory of today's Turkey) to the Krasnodar region began. By 1891, dozens of Armenian villages had already formed on the Black Sea coast of southern Russia. In 1896 the 14 thousand Armenians lived in the Black Sea region of Russia, in particular in such cities as Anapa, Novorossiysk, Tuapse, Sochi, Yekaterinodar (now Krasnodar), Yeysk, Armavir, and Maykop.

In Stavropol Krai Armenians began settling at the end of the XVIII century. Armenians were mainly engaged in trade, industrial production, and processing of agricultural products. According to the 1989 census, 72,530 Armenians lived in the region. Beginning in the late 1980s and early 1990s, new streams of Armenian migrants from Armenia and refugees from Azerbaijan and Abkhazia began arriving in Stavropol Krai. In 1993 Armenians made up 3% of the region's population after Russians and Karachays. In 2003 the 400,000 Armenians already lived in Stavropol Krai. Numerous Armenian communities were formed, schools, the Armenian church, youth and cultural organizations were opened.

It should be noted that 8 out of 10 Armenian respondents in Russia believed that the work they do is well paid, corresponds to their knowledge and abilities, and generally satisfies them. Thus, 6 out of 10 respondents rate their income status highly. The position “I have enough money to buy everything I consider necessary” was noted by 33% of respondents, and the position “I don't have enough money to buy a car or an apartment” was noted by 35% of respondents (Integration VS Repatriation, 2022: 78).

By the way, 9% of labor migrants, who arrived from Armenia, have their own homes in Russia, since many arrive with their families. Additionally, 72% of Armenian labor migrants live with family members, which is twice as many as among labor migrants from Central Asia (Endriushko, 2020: 84-95). Thus, conditions are emerging for the further aggregation of capital and property, which leads to the strengthening of the diaspora's position in various sectors of the economy. (Topilin, 2021: 116).

Moscow Armenians more often live in their own or rented apartments, while those from Krasnodar and Stavropol regions live in their own house or apartment. At the same time, Armenians living in Krasnodar (71.3%) more often rate their housing conditions as “good” and those living in Stavropol as “satisfactory” or “bad” (35.1% and 6.6%, respectively).

An important integration factor is the knowledge of the Russian language. Most of those born in Russia speak Russian very well (92%), but do not know Armenian (60%). More than

¹ <http://diaspora.gov.am/ru/pages/15/russia>

80% of those Armenians who have lived in Russia for up to 10 years speak Armenian very well and speak Russian very well. With years of migration, knowledge of the Russian language improves and Armenian is forgotten. One of the conditions for integration into Russian society is formal and informal social relationships of members of the Armenian diaspora with different groups in Russian society. Our study recorded a wide range of contacts with other ethnic groups in the Russian society.

Overcoming cultural differences and the integration of Armenian migrants are facilitated by mixed marriages, which create the basis for positive intercultural interaction within the diasporas in Russian society. According to our survey data 37.4% of Armenian respondents have interethnic families or mixed marriages (among the 29.7% of respondents they are Russians, and among the 7.7% of respondents they are representatives of other ethnic groups). But among young people, this indicator shows a higher degree of integration.

An important factor of integration is the mood that migrants experience in everyday life. According to our survey, 67% of the Armenian diaspora had a good, normal and smooth mood. Only 14.7% of them experienced anxiety and irritation; and 3.7% - fear, despair and hopelessness. The remaining 14.8% of respondents found it difficult to clearly characterize their emotional state (Poghosyan, Osadchaya, 2024: 133-147).

The extremely important characteristic of the integration results is identification, since it implies the acceptance by members of the Armenian diaspora of the corresponding group norms and rules of interaction in the society. Identifying themselves with Russia means that migrants attribute positive characteristics to Russian society. Thus, among Armenian migrants, 45% of respondents feel themselves citizens of Armenia; 14.3% feel themselves citizens of Russia; 10.2% feel representatives of the Armenian people; 7.1% feel simply members of their family; 6.6% feel as citizens of the world; and 6.6% feel residents of the city in which they live. As can be seen, when identifying, the official status of citizenship, and the ethnic and family identification, are met more often.

And even more significant indicator of the degree of integration of the members of the Armenian diaspora is the idea of their own life goals and future activity. About half of the Armenian migrants see themselves as citizens of Russia in the future (48.4%); a fifth see themselves as citizens of Russia and Armenia, i.e. both countries (20.1%); and 10% see themselves as citizens of Armenia; another 8% see themselves as citizens of a third country where they plan to move (Poghosyan, Osadchaya, 2024: 133-147). So, the majority of Armenian migrants intend to settle permanently in Russia.

However, that our survey was conducted in Russia before the start of the war in Ukraine. With the start of military actions in Ukraine and the introduction of tough sanctions against Russia, a big number of Russians left the country and about 120 thousand moved to Armenia. Among them, more than 25% were our compatriots who had previously left for work in Russia in different years. These migrants from Russia began to be called “relocants”, since the overwhelming majority of them moved to Armenia together with their businesses and even office employees. The large influx of “relocants” to Armenia provided a sharp economic effect, since serious investments were made in the banking sector and the country's economy, especially in the IT sector. As a result, in 2022, Armenia's overall GDP growth was a record 12%.

Economic grounds of Integration

During the post-Soviet years, Armenian diaspora and labor migrants sent about annually 1.5-2 billion US dollars from Russia, which amounted to about 10% of the country's GDP. In fact, this represented significant social assistance to the families in Armenia. Transfers to Armenia had different dynamics. Thus, the peak was in 2013 with an indicator of 19.7% of GDP. In 2019, the ratio of transfers to GDP was 11.2%, and in 2020 this ratio was 10.5%. But already

in 2022, a record figure of 30% of the country's GDP was again achieved. The picture of money transfers only in January of 2024 is presented below in Table 3. (Central Bank of Armenia, 2024).

Table 3.

	Countries	Inflow, mill. USD	Outflow, mill. USD
1.	Russia	234	40
2.	USA	45	42
3.	Europe (EU)	15	22
4.	Kazakhstan	3.1	1.3
5.	UAE	2.9	52
6.	China	0.97	6.6

As seen from Table 3, in January 2024, the largest inflow of financial transfers (\$234 million) to Armenia was from Russia, mainly from Armenian migrants working there. From the European countries (EU), the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and China, on the contrary, the outflow of financial resources from Armenia even significantly exceeded the inflow.

The 2024 marks the tenth anniversary of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), within which five CIS countries are implementing Eurasian economic integration. Over the past period, the economic union of the five countries has brought many benefits and advantages, in particular in terms of facilitating and expanding opportunities for international trade. For Armenia, the past years of economic integration have made it possible not only to support its economy, but also to significantly strengthening and developing trade and economic ties with the participating states, and in particular with Russia. After Armenia joined the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) in 2015, its exports to the Union countries increased by 3.45 times. Armenia's exports to Russia for 2015-2024 increased by 3.5 times, and imports by 3 times. This shows that the free movement of goods, services, capital and labor, the removal of customs duties in the EAEU play a much greater role than the presence of common borders (Armenia's Economic Outlook. 2024).

The historical feature of the Armenian economy is a stable surplus of labor resources, which determines a high level of migration outflow mainly to Russia, the CIS countries, the EU and the USA. The migration outflow significant increased after the war between Armenia and Azerbaijan in 2020. It is very important to take into account that not only traditionally the main flows of migration of Armenian labor resources are directed to Russia, but it is also the main economic partner of Armenia. Strong foreign trade relations between Armenia and Russia ensure food, energy and economic security of the republic. According to the official data of the Republic of Armenia, 98% of wheat, flour, sunflower oil and other grain crops are imported from Russia; almost 35% of all agricultural products and 39% of poultry; about 40% of fertilizers for agriculture (State Statistic Committee of Armenia, 2025) More than 50% of bakery and pasta exports, 96.7% of all fruit and vegetable and agricultural products of Armenia are sent to Russia (Trade map, 2025) Russia accounts for more than 95% of all exported fish, potatoes, tomatoes, apricots, cherries, peaches, plums and up to 87% of cheese, cottage cheese, water and alcoholic beverages (Trade map, 2025). It will be difficult to find alternative markets for Armenian products.

It should be noted that energy resources are supplied from Russia to Armenia at preferential prices (much lower than world prices), which provides more than 91.7% of all energy needs of the republic (Trade map, 2025). The refusal of these supplies may strongly affect the competitiveness of industries and lead to a significant drop in GDP. Russia remains the leading investor in the Armenian economy. The accumulated volume of Russian investments in Armenia as of October 2024 amounts to \$4 billion (EDB. MVI Evroregion Report. RU, 2024). The accelerated growth of the Armenian economy in 2022 (12.6%) and in 2023 (9.4%) was associated with the redistribution of part of the income due to the participation of Armenian

companies in the re-export of Russian goods (Eurasian Economic Commission, 2025). Gold was one of the first Russian export commodities to fall under an embargo following Moscow's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. Russian businesses are capitalizing on trading gold via Armenia, as the country does not apply export duties. Armenia are helping Russia bypass the Western embargo on the gold trade. According to Russian customs data obtained by *The Insider*, between 2022 and 2024 Armenia purchased 89 tons of gold from Russia valued at approximately \$5.2 billion. Armenia's total imports in 2022 of all products, not just gold, amounted to \$11 billion, while its GDP was \$19.5 billion (*The Insider*, 2025). In addition, a sharp transfer and receipts from Russian individuals who moved to Armenia for temporary residence, "relocators", as well as their investments in small businesses in Armenia, became a factor in economic growth. An even more significant contribution to the economic development of Armenia was made by the transfer of a number of Russian companies to Armenian jurisdiction in order to avoid US and EU "sanctions".

Meanwhile, the public opinion polls conducted in the participating countries indicate a decrease in the population's interest in the prospects of integration, due to a slight slowdown in integration processes and their inconsistency with the initially established social expectations. The sociological studies conducted over the past few years in Armenia also indicate a noticeable decline in the image of Russia as a friendly country and a reliable strategic partner of Armenia in the eyes of the Armenian public. The ruling political elite of the republic does not hide its intention to change the vector of geopolitical orientation from Russia and from EAEU to the West.

Many experts openly talk about the crisis in Armenian-Russian relations against the backdrop of Yerevan's rapprochement with the West. Strengthening Armenia's cooperation with the US, NATO and EU institutions does not provide real support for the country's development, its economy, defense and humanitarian sphere, which are naturally and historically based on the regional political field and, in particular, on the traditional relations with Russia. Armenia's continuing drift into the Western orbit increases the risk of losing all the benefits and opportunities from cooperation with Russia and the integration process in the Eurasian space.

Since the last summer, Armenia has declared the development of relations with the United States to the level of "strategic partnership." And on January 14, 2025, the Charter on Strategic Partnership between the United States and Armenia was signed. At the same time, Armenia formally continues to be an ally of the Russian Federation under the terms of the Treaty of Friendship, Cooperation, and Mutual Assistance of August 29, 1997. The Armenian leadership has expressed its intention to diversify trade and economic ties through partnership with Western countries. The legal basis for the partnership between Armenia and the EU is the Comprehensive and Enhanced Partnership Agreement, which was signed on November 24, 2017, and entered into force on March 1, 2021. On February 12, 2025, the Armenian Parliament adopted a law on the beginning of the country's accession process to the European Union. At the same time, the government cannot refuse the economic benefits for Armenia as a member of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU)².

By the way, during the 2018-2024, the migration flows of Armenia labor forces to Russia remained at approximately the same level. The exception was in 2019-2020, due to COVID restrictions. Finally, it should be noted that a significant problem for the Armenian economy is its dependence on migrant remittances and assistance from Armenian diasporas in Russia, the United States and the EU. Migrant remittances averaged 14% of GDP per year in 1995-2020. In

² https://golosarmenii.am/article/228249/%C2%ABslepye-shagi-pashinyana%C2%BB-rossijskij-ekspert-o-tom--chto-terpenie-moskvy-akanchivaetsya?fbclid=IwY2xjawIO3WBleHRuA2FlbQIxMQABHSg2KYDg_RaoWUtrv3-IqHT8_Sr46LzgM8mwnBgJvKAWOoF9dCpQH5CYxg_aem_rWKz_ypIHMLdxqurcQPcNQ (accessed: 10.02.2025)

January-September 2024 the total inflow of remittances from abroad reached almost \$4 billion. More than \$2.57 billion of them were transferred from the Armenian diaspora in Russia (Armenia`s Economic Outlook, 2024). The GDP per capita ratio in Armenia is almost three times lower than in Russia. The GDP per capita indicator in Russia generally characterizes the potential of the Armenian diaspora in Russia (World Economic Outlook, 2020).

Conclusion

The Republic of Armenia entry into the Eurasian Economic Union in 2015, the intensification of migration exchange and the growth of the Armenian diaspora in Russia open up new opportunities for the implementation of the socio-economic potential of the Armenian diaspora in Russia. Studying the phenomenon of the Armenian diaspora, identifying the features of their adaptation and integration, as well as self-organization of migrants, form the basis for the economic prosperity, cultural integration and stability of diaspora.

The conceptual definition of social integration of the Armenian diaspora as a key concept allowed us to determine the main resource of its measurement and interpretation. Our survey revealed the main mechanisms for the formation of connections, forms of exchange and interaction of Armenian diaspora with the Russian population. Considering the role of the Armenian diaspora in the socio-economic processes of Russia, its influence on all spheres of life of the country, as a host state, in the context of the intensification of emigration of Armenians to Russia after Armenia's entry into the Eurasian Economic Union, formed a new social reality that changed the role and place of the Armenian diaspora as an ethnocultural and socio-economic phenomenon.

Our sociological survey was based on the concept of the phenomenon of “integration” as a result of successful integration of Armenians into the structure of Russian society. As the survey showed, subjective assessments of Armenians in the regions of Russia demonstrate relative stability and relatively high intensity of integration, as well as active inclusion of them in Russian society. The analysis of the obtained results allows us to conclude that there is a fairly high degree of integration of the Armenian diaspora, including youth, into the social, economic and cultural life in Russia. At the same time, it was revealed that only a small part of the Armenian diaspora intends to potentially repatriate back to homeland.

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